

Title: Stream Analytics Technologies – Comparison and Experiences

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INTRODUCTION:

The design and implementation of stream analytics solutions is challenging for companies who face gazillion of data that needs to be processed in real-time or near real-time. This study will provide some insight on available solutions and demonstrate some experiences.

AIM:

A brighter view on streaming analytics solutions and introducing applied solutions.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A review on previous studies, rankings, comparisons and features of the available stream analytics solutions. The ranking, comparisons and features have been extracted from Gartner, Forester Wave, Microsoft Azure, Hortonworks and some academic journals. Also experimental studies on applied stream analytics solutions for 2 different clients was conducted. Their features have been analyzed and the difficulties on implementation have been revealed and discussed. These 2 stream analytics solutions are an Azure Stream Analytics project and a combination of Kafka and Storm on Hortonworks.

RESULTS:

Stream analytics solutions have been discussed and categorized based on their features, advantages and disadvantages. The possibility of the combined solutions have been studied and in one of the experiments, which combined Kafka and Storm, reveals that this combined solution guarantees the data quality and reliability significantly.

CONCLUSIONS:

The results of this study conclude that there is no specific best practice that can be applied to different problem domains or industries and there is a need to study case by case. Also combination of solutions would be a viable option.

KEYWORDS:

Streaming Analytics; Data Stream Technologies; Data Stream Best Practices; Data Stream Comparisons

BIOGRAPHY:

David Zall has completed his Master Degree in Computer Science from BTH University, Sweden. He is a Big Data Consultant for CGI, the 5th biggest IT Company. He has been involved in many architectural design, and implementation of data solutions for financial, banking and

hospitality companies. Currently he is working on the Data-Hub project for National Bank of Canada. He also has a number of publications on the data science and data visualization.